

FERGANA VALLEY IN THE 40S OF THE XVII CENTURY

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Abstract: This article analyzes the political life of the Ferghana Valley, the eastern region of the Bukhara Khanate, during the reign of Nadrmuhammad Khan (1642-1645) through sources and scientific literature.

Keywords: Khanate of Bukhara, Ashtarkhanids, Andijan, Abdurahman divanbegi, nomads.

ФЕРГАНСКАЯ ДОЛИНА В 40-Х ГОДАХ XVII ВЕКА

Аннотация: В этой статье анализируется политическая жизнь Ферганской долины, восточной территории Бухарского ханства во время правления Надр Мухаммед-хана (1642-1645), с помощью источников и научной литературы.

Ключевые слова: Бухарское ханство, аштарханиды, Андижан, Абдурахман дивонбеги, кочевники.

INTRODUCTION

During the reign of Imamkulikhan who was the strongest representative of the Ashtarkhani dynasty, the Bukhara Khanate became politically stronger. The political situation in the southwestern part of the country improved after the death of the Iranian Shah Abbas I, due to the weakening of the Safavid state and friendly relations with the Baburi Shah Jahangir. In the north-eastern borders of the Xhanate, after a long period of intense fighting with nomadic Kazakhs, control over the Fergana Valley and Tashkent was established for a certain time, but the situation was still anxious. Intensification of constant attacks on the Kazakh Xhanate by the Jungians led to the migration of Kazakhs and Kyrgyz from Yeti-su to the interior of the region. This caused another conflict in the northeastern regions of the Sirdarya River and Ferghana Valley. By the last periods of Imamkulikhan's reign, as a result of health problems, the influence of local emirs on the central government began to gradually increase. Therefore, Imamkulikhan voluntarily gave up the throne to his brother Nadirmuhammed.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Nadrmuhammad Khan (1642-1645) had 12 children and distributed the main parts of the Khanate to his relatives. At this point, it is permissible to mention one aspect of the Khanate. The Khanate of Bukhara was practically divided into two parts, a high dargah centered in Bukhara and a smaller dargah in the city of Balkh, ruled by the crown prince. The Ferghana Valley, located in the eastern part of the

Khanate, was also under the control of the Ashtarkhanids. In the treaty of friendship concluded with the Russian king Mikhail Feodorovich of Nadrmuhammad Khan, he lists Andijan and Fergana among the territories under his control [3: 135]. Therefore, the complete rule of the Ashtarkhanids was established in the valley.

Nadrmuhammad Khan brought his children Abdulaziz Khan and Bakhram sultan and trusted emirs to Movarunnahr. Samarkand was given to Abdulaziz Khan, and Tashkent was given to Bakhram sultan. In order to help his children in the management, he appoints Bek ughli to Abdulaziz Khan, and Bakibi Yuz to Bakhram sultan as the atalig [1: 213]. Although there is no clear information about who ruled the valley on behalf of the Ashtarkhanids in the sources, some comments can be made based on "Silsilat al-Salatin" and vakf documents related to Ferghana. The name of Bakhram sultan is mentioned in two documents dated 1053 AH (1643-1644) given to the sayyids of Koroskon [5: 92, 120]. Similar information was also given by Zaki Walidi and only the document in it shows the date as 1652 [4: 77]. It is natural that there is an error in the date of the document cited by Z. Walidi, because in 1652 Bakhram sultan was not in Movarounnahr. In 1645, after Nadrmuhammad Khan lost his power in Bukhara, he came to Balkh and divided his territories among his children. Bakhram sultan was awarded the territory of Kolob [7: 95]. Therefore, it is controversial that the date of the document in which his name is mentioned is 1652. "Silsilat al-salatin" also contains valuable notes about the valley. The emirs of Andijan, who complained about the Kyrgyz attack, also asked for a governor to be sent to them. As a result, it is written that Abdurahman Divanbegi was chosen as the governor of Andijan. So, during the time of Nadrmuhammad Khan, the Ferghana Valley was divided into two parts. The northern part of Syrdarya was ruled by Bakhrom sultan, while the southern parts of the river together with Andijan were under the rule of Abdurahman Divanbegi. This administrative division in the valley can also be traced back to the Timurid period. This situation was reflected in the 1500 peace treaty between Mirza Babur and his brother Mirza Jahangir [11: 212]. Although it is not clearly stated in the sources who was in charge of Khojand during this period, if we take into account that the Bakibi rebellion took place in this city in the last years of Nadrmuhammad Khan's reign, it is most likely that Khojand was under the control of this emir as part of the Tashkent estate. Because such a situation occurs during the reign of Baqimuhammad Khan (1601-1605). During his time, the southern part of the valley was managed by the atalig Sarhunbi Jaloyir on behalf of the crown prince Valimuhammad Khan .

In the work "*Tarikh-i Muqim Khani*" it is written that there was no king as rich as Nadrmuhammad Khan among the Shibani and Ashtarkhanids [7: 94]. At the beginning of his reign, Nadrmuhammad Khan tried to strengthen the central power

by using his wealth to sway the big amirs of his brother's time to his side. But unrest remained in the northeastern regions of the Khanate. Since 1636, Kazakhs have been living in peace with the Khanate of Bukhara, but the constant attacks of the nomadic Djungar tribes on Yeti-su and Eastern Turkistan were increasing. As a result, it was natural that the movement of a large number of Kazakh and Kyrgyz tribes there towards the Bukhara Khanate would cause political tension in Tashkent and the Fergana Valley. That is why Nadrmuhammad Khan sent his trusted emirs under the leadership of Nazarbi baruti to "regulate affairs" in Andijan [9: 47]. Although the author of "History of Kipchakkhan" wrote about this, he did not mention the activities of these emirs in the valley. The work "Silsilat al-Salotin" gives detailed information about this. While the military forces of the Ashtarkhanids were suppressing the unrest in Tashkent and Khojand, the emirs of Andijan complained to the Khan of Bukhara that the nomadic Kyrgyz tribes were threatening their property. Taking advantage of this situation, Nairmuhammad Khan, who wanted to strengthen his position in the eastern part of the Ferghana Valley, immediately sent Abdurakhman devonbegi against the Kyrgyz. Abdurakhman Divanbegi first starts the work with a meeting with the Kazakh Khan Jakhangir Khan. It can be seen that the meeting was successful from the fact that Abdulaziz Khan and Kazakh Khan's daughter Kazakhkhanim were betrothed and the united forces set out to punish the Kyrgyz [10: 128]. The sons of Kyrgyz leader Qutlugh Sayyid, Tilakibi and Karakhitai Mirza, join the battle against the allied forces with other leaders. Sources do not say where the two sides clashed. Qutlugh Sayyid and dozens of other Kyrgyz commanders were killed in a fierce battle. As a result, the security of the eastern parts of the country was ensured. Judging from the above two sources, in fact, Nadrmuhammad Khan sent Abdurakhman Divanbegi to the valley accompanied by the amirs like Nazarbi Buruti. Although the reason was the raids of nomadic Kyrgyz, Nadrmuhammad Khan aimed to strengthen his influence in the valley. Therefore, he sent his friend Abdurrahman Divanbegi as his most reliable representative. Interestingly, neither the name of Bakhram sultan nor the name of Bakibi Yuz are mentioned in any of the events. The betrothal of the Kazakh Khan Jakhangir Khan's daughter to Samarkand Governor Abdulaziz Khan by Abdurakhman Divanbegi was not in favor of Bakhram sultan's Bagibi Yuz atalig. Because the atalig who ruled Tashkent and Khojand remained among the properties belonging to his rivals. That is why Bukharakhan, through his son Abdulaziz Khan and Abdurakhman Divanbegi, strengthened his influence in these regions by forming an alliance with the Kazakhs and striking the Kyrgyz. Shortly after that, in 1643, the next march of the Djungars to the Kazakh lands began. Kazakh Khan Jakhangir Khan asks for help from Bukharakhan, Nadrmuhammad Khan sends an army of twenty thousand people

under the leadership of Yalangtosh Bahadir. O. Burton notes that together with Yalangtosh Bahadir, Abdulaziz Khan and Abdurakhman Divanbegi also went to help the Kazakhs and that Abdurakhman Divanbegi ruled Andijan from 1642 [1: 220]. So, Andijan troops led by Abdurakhman Divanbegi also participated in the famous Orbulok battle. The Djungars, who were defeated in the battle of Orbulok, attacked Tashkent from Koggis. Abdulaziz Khan was saved from defeat by Yalangtosh Bahadir and Abdurrahman Divanbegi, who came to help in time. Although the Kalmyk attack was repelled, the situation in the north-east of the country was alarming.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In 1645, a disagreement arose between Sultan Bakhrom and Bagibi Yuz in Tashkent. As a result, Nadrmuhammad Khan Bakhrom recalled the sultan and sent Abdurakhman Divanbegi to the direction of Bakibi Yuz. Although Bakibi Yuz was persuaded to go to Bukhara, he doubted the khan's impartiality towards him and entered the city of Khojand [1: 226]. After learning about this, Nadrmuhammad Khan sent his son Abdulaziz Khan with a number of emirs against him. According to the work "History of Muqimkhan", the forces disaffected with Nadrmuhammad Khan explained to the khan that it was necessary to send a large army there, under the pretext that nomadic Kazakhs had attacked Khojand. The Khan sends an army under the leadership of his son Abdulaziz Khan. At this time, Bakibi Yuz found a hundred Kazakh princes and entered the city of Khojand. Abdulaziz Khan came to the city and killed this prince, and the conspirators asked Abdulaziz Khan to take the throne of Bukhara. After being told that otherwise they can kill him too, Abdulaziz Khan agreed to their condition [7:94]. In the work "History of Kipchak", Bakibi does not give any information about the face at all, but states that he is Sanjar, the grandson of the Kazakh prince Imamkulikhan [6: 752]. The historian of the Kokand Khanate, Muhammadhakimkhan, in his work "Muntahab ut Tawarikh" limits himself to mentioning the Bakibi Yuz in the event of Khojand [12: 666]. "Matlab ut Talibin", an important source that illuminates the life of the sheikhs of Dzhoybor, also contains information about the participants of these events. "At that time," it is written in the work, "Bakibi Yuz and all the emirs of Imamkulikhan expressed their opposition (to Nadrmuhammad Khan). Nadrmuhammad Khan sent his eldest son Abdulaziz Khan against them. Rakhimbek, Bek ughli, Sevinchbi, Muhammadyorbi, Nazirbi and others appealed to the sultan: We will remove your father from the kingdom and put you on the throne. If you accept it - very good, otherwise we will expel both of you from the region" [2: 247]. We can get detailed information about the rebellion of the eternal face from the work "Silsilat al-Salotin". Those who are dissatisfied with Nadrmuhammad Khan send Bakibi and a Kazakh prince to

Khojand. After the Bukhara army led by Abdulaziz Khan besieged Khojand for 15 days, the great emirs told the prince of Bukhara to release the city from the siege, wait for him on the river, and bring Bakibi Yuz to him. As they said, when Abdulaziz Khan retreated to the river, emirs like Mominbi and Qazaqbi came to him and told them some conditions in exchange for suppressing Bakibi's rebellion. From now on, they declare that they will not obey Nadrmuhammad Khan, that the khan and Balkh troops will leave Movarounnahr under the leadership of Abdurahman Divanbegi, and that the power of Bukhara should be managed by Abdulaziz Khan [10: 129-130]. Abdulaziz Khan has no choice but to accept these conditions. As a result, Abdulaziz Khan returned to Bukhara from Khojand and took power. His father fled to Balkh and limited himself to managing his former territories. This meant that the Khanate of Bukhara was practically divided into two.

In the works "Matlab ut-Talibin", "Tarikh-i Qipchaq Khani", "Silsilat al-Salatin" the information about the Khojand uprising is characterized by their proximity to each other, while in the work "Tarikh-i Mukim Khani" it is noted that the Khojand uprising was organized under the pretext of an attack by Kazakhs.

CONCLUSION

So, the political situation in the Ferghana Valley during Nadrmuhammad Khan's time was unstable due to internal and external factors. On the one hand, the region was threatened by the nomadic Jungars and Kyrgyz from the northeast, and on the other hand, the forces dissatisfied with the policy of Nadrmuhammad Khan rose up against the Khan from the valley and achieved their goals. As a result, the Khanate of Bukhara was practically divided into two parts, the center of which was Bukhara and Balkh.

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